

D6.1 SPATIAL IMPACT MASTER PLAN

Revision: v.1.1

Work package	WP 6
Task	Task 6.1
Due date	28/02/2022
Submission date	28/02/2022
Deliverable lead	AUSTRALO
Version	1.1
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Grant Agreement No.: 101021808

Call: H2020-SU-DS-2020

Topic: SU-DS02-2020

Type of Action: RIA

Abstract	This document outlines the master plan for the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies designed for the project. The plan also provides an overview of the stakeholder base to target, as well as a standardization landscape as the basis for further standardization activities in the project.
Keywords	IMPACT, DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V1.1	22-02-2022	Reviewed by coordinator and Quality Manager	TUD, UT
V1.0	15-02-2022	First version	AUSTRALO, MAINFLUX, FOKUS, UCD ...

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SPATIAL project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Research innovation is a driving force for economic growth, the creation of new job opportunities and the enhancement of the standard of living. It is therefore important to ensure that the knowledge generated within research and innovation projects is properly diffused and that the means through which such knowledge can be delivered to the society are being effectively explored. This is realized through the commercial exploitation of products and services, which is the primary way of delivering research results to the citizens (end-users). In addition, communicating research results can effectively accelerate research and technical development (RTD) towards increasing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL), going beyond the current state of the art, and even creating new research horizon lines on future and emerging trends. Furthermore, dissemination activities, such as participation in workshops or publication of information in websites, enable participants “to get feedback on the economic potential and recommended market-oriented exploitation pathways”.¹

The current document outlines the initial **SPATIAL IMPACT MASTER PLAN** consisting of the overall project dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies including an extensive overview of the standardization landscape in the area of SPATIAL and will be the basis for further standardization activities in the project.

The plan is the result of a coordinated effort among partners, considering stakeholders' categories and needs as well as partners' communication channels and tools. In this sense, it is a supporting tool for each partner in maximizing the impact of their own dissemination actions while providing means to ensure high visibility of activities and outcomes of the project as a whole. This plan proposes a list of suitable communication & dissemination tools and activities for engaging the target groups in the project. To this end, a multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed in order to maximize the impact of the dissemination

¹ [Http://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/14ff6fe1-023d-4291-8c4d-4ae779aa78a4.0001.02/DOC_1](http://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/14ff6fe1-023d-4291-8c4d-4ae779aa78a4.0001.02/DOC_1)

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activities, adjusting the materials and tools to the specific needs, interests and potential for involvement of the target audience.

The consortium considers this plan as a living document, reflecting an open, ongoing dialogue with potential users and related networks during the project, in order to be inclusive and to ensure the best possible results.

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1 AGILE STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT

1.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is an activity often referred to as 'community building' and it is a key aspect of every H2020 project, such as SPATIAL. Indeed, the programme relies on communities, initiatives and projects that will either use the outcomes or relate and possibly liaise with its activities along its course.

Creating and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is always a crucial factor in the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholder's impact on a project depends on its potential power -the ability to influence the value proposition- and the interest in exercising that power. Assessing the relative levels of each supports the decision on whom to spend time and effort to realize the greatest benefits.

When it comes to addressing fundamental challenges in Research and Innovation, multiple initiatives often work in a standalone manner to address the same issue from multiple directions, incurring in inefficiencies and being incapable of delivering their full potential. By adopting an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups that can benefit and contribute to the impact of the project, SPATIAL will be able to reach a deeper understanding of the requirements and benefits from aligning efforts with similar task forces as it requires a responsive growth factor capable of prospecting and creating brand new synergies over the project's lifetime, facilitating a greater advantage and extending its range of action.

1.1.1 ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

To maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination, communication & exploitation plans that will be introduced in this document, the consortium requires a mechanism for managing in a systematic manner the ever-changing list of organisations, initiatives, and players with a position to influence the value streams of the project.

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For this reason, **SPATIAL** will implement an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement** framework, designed to continuously developing and strengthening relationships with a significant audience through the values of the **Agile Manifesto**²:

The Agile Manifesto principles		
Individuals and interactions	over	Processes and tools
Results		Comprehensive documentation
Collaboration		Formality
Responding to change		Following a plan

TABLE 1. AGILE MANIFESTO PRINCIPLES

- **Individuals and interactions over processes and tools:** Ecosystem building is a team- based approach to deliver value as a joint effort. Tools are an important part of projects, but the team needs to work together effectively through productive interactions with the stakeholders.
- **Results over comprehensive documentation:** It is much more valuable to interact with the stakeholders, obtaining continuous feedback and managing increments of the ecosystem's snapshot rather than overspending resources in studying and reporting about their profiles and potential objectives.
- **Collaboration over formality:** This framework is designed to promote and facilitate collaboration in the programme. The team aims to engage and collaborate with stakeholders to inspect and adapt the vision, so the project will be as valuable as possible.
- **Responding to change over following a plan:** Rather than maintaining a fully defined and static vision of the stakeholders from the project, this methodology focuses on building up an ecosystem of interested parts throughout its lifetime.

² The principles can be found on <https://agilemanifesto.org/principles.html>

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The framework follows an iterative implementation structure based on Sprints, time-boxes of 6 months where the main goal is to incrementally increase and reinforce the engagement of the stakeholders with the initiative. A new Sprint starts immediately after the conclusion of the previous Sprint at the end of each quarter of the project (Sprint Qx, where x is the quarter number starting at 1). Its workflow includes the following phases:

- **Phase 1 – Scouting:** Building upon the objectives of **SPATIAL** and the findings from previous Sprints, this phase will explore, map and assess Target Groups -and specific candidates- with different degrees of relevance for the scope and impact of the work plan. **SPATIAL** will build upon the sound experience and active involvement of the consortium members in initiatives and players that must be considered as baseline for engagement, taking advantage of new leads generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as outcome of the Interaction phase, including emerging Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and H2020 projects. The key result will be a version of the ‘Stakeholder Map’, a graphical instrument to list key actors -and specific candidates within them; 2) thoughtfully organise and correlate these audiences; 3) define a common terminology to be used in all the project’s reference.
- **Phase 2 – Interaction:** Next stage will imply the interaction as such with the identified target groups, supporting the activities outlined in the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies. This is the phase where **SPATIAL** will collaborate with initiatives having a specific mandate on industrial digitisation. Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific Task Forces and Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications and participate in events. Feedback extrapolated from previous Sprints will be used to enhance the efficiency and impact of these measures.
- **Phase 3 – Learning:** From the actions performed during the interaction, the consortium will learn lessons and collect findings that will feed the next Sprint. This will also include insights obtained from consultation (e.g. in the form of quick questionnaires or interviews), gathering valuable external remarks about the project and its operation.

1.1.2 TARGET AUDIENCES & STAKEHOLDERS

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Promoting SPATIAL and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the initiative requires understanding who the 'target audience' is. Understanding these profiles and their influence in the value chain is essential to craft the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plans.

FIGURE 1. STAKEHOLDERS' GROUP

- **AI Developers/ Engineers:** SPATIAL will create meaningful interactions with developers and engineers pledged to technology innovations, research contributions, capacity building, and business activities related to the application of trustworthy AI in ICT systems. This category encompasses the foremost beneficiaries of the project in the uptake and advanced development of accountability features, advanced privacy management, data quality enforcement, and resilience when developing next-generation human-centric AI solutions. Developers represent the main audience of the trusted execution environment, guidelines and the educational module envisioned in the scope of the project.

SPATIAL will leverage the position of the consortium in strategic AI-driven communities to reach out to a critical mass of this audience (detailed references in section 4). This includes the most relevant initiatives in data governance, infrastructure and trustworthy AI from Europe, such as: **AI4EU**, the European Artificial Intelligence On-Demand Platform, and in

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particular its Ethical Observatory; the **European AI Alliance**, the multi-stakeholder forum promoted by the EC; the **Next Generation Internet** (NGI), empowering a human-centric Internet vision; the **Big Data Value Association** (BDVA), along with its links with the upcoming European Partnership on Artificial Intelligence, Data and Robotics. Additionally, it is worth noting the capacity of the project to create a **multi-national network of students** brought by four referent academic partners (TUD, UCD, UT, EUR), complemented by the Advisory Board, and the customer base provided by REA, MI and FOKUS.

- **Society as a whole:** SPATIAL will encourage faster uptake of AI technology by the European society, promoting the transparent and explainable nature of the value proposition by the project as an underlying substrate for the connected society.
- **End user sectors:** AI is meant to solve -or reduce drastically- technical challenges in critical end use sectors as they are increasingly reliant on data for decision-making. At the same time, they need to rely on transparent, explainable and resilient mechanisms, and some AI systems have demonstrated bias. For this reason, the project has the ambition to upscale trust, demonstrating and validating the value proposition in a number of use case scenarios led by industrial referents such as TID, FOKUS, NEC and F-Secure to 1) obtaining requirements and feedback to support the implementation of the project; 2) facilitating access to data collection; and 3) raising awareness on the advantages for application in real-world scenarios. SPATIAL will benefit from the membership of partners in strategic communities such as the 5G Infrastructure Association/ 5G Public-Private Partnership (5G PPP) -including representation in NetWorld2020 SME WG, led by AUS, and with MI-, O-RAN Alliance, SIGMOBILE, IoT Catalan Alliance DIH and European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities to amplify the outreach capacity through their channels and Working Groups. Additionally, this will allow the project to seize the opportunity to better position with views to forthcoming Horizon Europe partnerships and clusters, such as the Smart Networks and Services and Key Digital Technologies (KDT).
- **Policy makers:** Members of a government department, legislature, or other organisations responsible for making new policies and for promoting strategies around trustworthy AI. In the case of SPATIAL, the main references will be the European Union Agency for

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Cybersecurity (ENISA), and the European Commission, where the project will seek synergies with the ambition of the European Digital Strategy for the period 2020-2025, in particular in alignment with the strategic position towards Artificial Intelligence.

- **Cybersecurity providers:** Together with the AI developers, this category is of paramount relevance to deliver the objectives of SPATIAL, targeting security and privacy management service providers. Cooperation with the cybersecurity sector will ensure the application of transparency and explainability of AI in the development of security solutions, participating in the publication of research insights, technical implementations, contribution to standards, and amplification of awareness. It is of particular relevance the synergies foresaw with the four pilot projects under H2020-SU-ICT-03-2018 “Establishing and operating a pilot for a Cybersecurity Competence Network to develop and implement a common Cybersecurity Research & Innovation Roadmap”, namely CONCORDIA (via TID), CyberSec4Europe (via TUD, NEC, UCD), ECHO (via TID) and SPARTA (via FOKUS, UT). Furthermore, SPATIAL will seek twinning activities with the projects to be funded under the topic under consideration H2020- SU-DS02, reinforcing the impact of joint outreach actions. The active participation of FSC, TID and UT as members of the European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO) - reinforced by the explicit endorsement of this organization in the form of a Letter of Support- will enable a sound alliance with the activities of the Cyber Security Public-Private Partnership, as well as an advocacy effect among over 250 members of the European security industry and research community. It will be also relevant to connect with other actors related to the call under which SPATIAL was founded, in the way to pursue synergies among parallel projects. The projects within this topic are IDUNN, ERATOSTHENES, ARCADIAN IoT, IRIS, SECANT and TESTABLE.

1.2 STAKEHOLDERS MAP

Figure 1 contains the first version of the SPATIAL Stakeholders Map, that graphically summarises all the target audiences at this stage. Such diagram has been defined by taking into consideration the different target stakeholders' groups identified so far, as the outcome of, the ongoing, Sprint Q1 of the Agile Stakeholder Framework.

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The development of the Stakeholders Map was done based on a mind map which is annexed in the Appendix A of this deliverable.

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2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

Dissemination in Research and Innovation Projects is a key and necessary element for achieving the desired impact of the project. According to the European Commission, “*Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers*). *By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.*”³

2.1 DISSEMINATION PLAN

To this end, **SPATIAL** has developed a flexible and adjustable Dissemination Plan that aims on building effective awareness of the project results, creating understanding and aiming for action among the key target audience identified. The execution of this strategy will facilitate the best use and uptake of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project lifetime, reinforcing each of the impacts aimed in the work plan.

2.1.1 3 PHASES APPROACH

Dissemination activities will be carried out in three main phases. Each of these has specific objectives and will therefore perform specific actions using appropriate channels. These phases will be presented and discussed at the beginning of the project and will be refined accordingly to match the priorities of SPATIAL.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

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FIGURE 2. THREE PHASES APPROACH.

- **Phase I: Analysis (M01-M06).** In this preliminary phase, the Consortium will analyse the project's framework, with a special attention to internal and external barriers and obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities, as well as it will define the priorities and actions for the first year of the project. The Dissemination & Communication Leader will coordinate the engagement activities, to align the dissemination activities with the needs of the stakeholders identified, creating general awareness about the project's objectives and expected results. During this phase, a first set of promotional material, produced in the frame of SPATIAL communication plan will be prepared and delivered.
- **Phase II: Increase impact (M06-M18).** The main objective of Phase II is to increase impact and awareness generated during Phase I and to expose mainly the SPATIAL achievements. The Dissemination & Communication Leader will adapt the channels and measures identified in the proposal phase (and refined during Phase I) to the specific needs of Phase II, and it will work to properly find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results. Participation in workshops, organisations of ad hoc events, as well as organisation of tutorials/webinars (if needed) will boost the dissemination process. Specific Public Relations (PR) material will be also produced.

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- **Phase III: Adoption (M18-M36).** This phase will leverage the general awareness raised in Phase I and Phase II, attracting more potential users and customers of SPATIAL project's results. The Dissemination & Communication Leader together with the Exploitation Leader will evaluate the outcomes of Phase I and II and, if needed, it will refine the priorities, channels and measures previously settled, also in concertation with the agile stakeholder management activities. Secondly, it will define the main activities that could increase the impact also beyond the project's lifetime, such as continuing use of events, participation in workshops and conferences, contributions to publications in targeted specific media online and printed trade and research journals.

2.1.2 OBJECTIVES

The main and key objectives of the dissemination strategy are as follows:

1. To set up the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of the project.
2. To establish, maintain and grow a community around the project in coordination with the stakeholder management framework.
3. To create visibility and promote the work and results for target stakeholders by creating promotional material and online campaigns.
4. To disseminate project and outcomes to the widest possible community through various channels and instruments. External participation and knowledge sharing will be encouraged through networking activities and events aimed at increasing the impact potential and enriching the contribution to the project.
5. To conduct liaison with other EU, national and international initiatives to maximise the impact.

2.1.3 MEASURES

In order to execute the dissemination plan, the consortium has identified a number of measures that need to be implemented throughout the project, enabling it to reach the above-mentioned objectives, in the most efficient and effective way.

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MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefit of the measure	Stakeholders
Project documentation	Documentation material in the form of public deliverables will be made available through SPATIAL ⁴ 's public repository, as well as CORDIS ⁵ , and communicated through our communication channels	Publicly available information which can be disseminated and infused to similar to SPATIAL initiative and into the community as a whole.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.
Peer-reviewed publications	SPATIAL aims at publishing and contributing to peer-reviewed publications in top refereed scientific journals and conferences relevant for digital construction. As a RIA project, one of the primary objectives is to ensure the technical achievements and experimental findings of the project will be known and	Disseminate the outcomes of the project to a wide scientific community. Showcasing outcomes makes available to the scientific community for further exploitation.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.

⁴ [SPATIAL h2020 Project | Zenodo](#)

⁵ [CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

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	exploited by a larger research community and related scientific domains.		
Technical Publications	SPATIAL consortium, the project will publish and contribute to technical blogs and articles or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up), as well as references related to the use case application domains under consideration (topdown)	Technical articles can disseminate the project's views and outcomes to a wider scientific and technical audience, leveraging project's impact.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.

ONLINE CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit of the measure	Stakeholders
Open Access	Following the principle 'as open as possible', SPATIAL will provide open access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data, following the Data Management Plan. SPATIAL is	"Open Access" Scientific & Technical material allows a wider dissemination of the project's outcome to a wider scientific and technological community.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.

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	using Zenodo ⁶ repository, where it is possible to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them. The Zenodo infrastructure is also used a document repository for all public deliverables.		
Social Networks	SPATIAL manages an online community through its social media channels: Twitter ⁷ & LinkedIn ⁸ .	The use of social media is to provide links to publications and presentation files and leverage awareness about the SPATIAL project.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.
Website	The main resource for generic promotion of the project activities and results to all target audiences, providing comprehensive information about SPATIAL.	It serves as s 'Point of Market Entry' and it shows the mission, the ambition, the project as a whole, pilot cases and consortium information.	AI developers/Engineers Cybersecurity providers. Society. End users' sectors. Policy makers.

⁶ [SPATIAL h2020 Project | Zenodo](#)

⁷ [SPATIAL Project \(@SPATIAL_H2020\) / Twitter](#)

⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/spatial-h2020>

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EVENTS			
Measure	Description	Benefit of the measure	Stakeholders
Conferences	The consortium will disseminate outcomes achieved by the project in the form of presentations, talks and personal engagement. This action will include events directly related to SPATIAL, but also end use-oriented affairs with a focus on digital transformation.	Participating in conferences, workshops and trade fairs is a strategic mechanism to interact actively with multiple stakeholders at a time.	All stakeholders
Exhibition demos	As an initiative targeting applied technology, one of the objectives of the project is to showcase and validate in public the outcomes achieved. Hence, SPATIAL will include in the plan some exhibition activities and demos to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed capabilities.	Showcasing the project's tangible outcomes through exhibitions and demo events, allows the dissemination of concrete outcomes to a wider audience.	All stakeholders

TABLE 2 MEASURES TO MAXIMISE DISSEMINATION.

2.1.3.1 Events list

The list below is an indicative list of events that have identified as main targets. This list is continuously updated by all project partners while actions per event and per partner are being identified and assigned, depending on the maturity of the project. It is also crucial to mention that a lot of events (if not all of them) are transforming to virtual (from physical) as a consequence of the current Covid-19 emergency. In any case, **SPATIAL** will seek to get involved regardless the form of the event.

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EVENT	DATE	LOCATION	LINK
Eco6G	10/02/2022	ONLINE	https://eco6g.com/
Sicur 2022	22-25/02/2022	Madrid, ES	https://www.ifema.es/sicur
MWC Barcelona	28/02- 03/03/2022	Barcelona, ES	https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/
NGI Forum 2022	tbd	ONLINE	https://2022.ngiforum.eu/
IoT Solutions World Congress	10-12/05/2022	Barcelona, ES	https://www.iotsworldcongress.com/
FIC- International Cybersecurity Forum	07-09/06/2022	Lille, FR	https://www.forum-fic.com
European Cyber Week	tbd	Rennes, FR	https://www.montimage.com/news/ecw2021
Cybercrime Con 2022	tbd	ONLINE	https://cybercrimecon.com/
Eco6G	10/02/2022	ONLINE	https://eco6g.com/

TABLE 3. INTERESTING EVENTS FOR 2022.

2.1.3.2 Conferences and Journals list

The following list introduces some of the conferences and journals that the project will emphasize on. However, this list is dynamic and gets updated on a frequent basis according to the scientific and technical maturity of the project. Note most of the conferences are linked to some sort of journal publication via proceedings or other editorial services.

CONFERENCE	DATE	LOCATION	LINK
ITEQS	24/01/2022	ONLINE	http://www.mrtc.mdh.se/ITEQS/2022/
European Cyber Defence and Cybersecurity Forum	25/01/2022	ONLINE	https://cybersecforum.eu/
ACM HotMobile	9- 10/03/2022	Tempe, US	https://hotmobile.org/2022/

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Cybersecurity Standardisation Conference 2022	15/03/2022	ONLINE	Link
Percom 2022	21-25/03/2022	ONLINE	https://www.percomm.org
EU Cybersecurity Act	24-25/03/2022	Brussels, BE	https://eucyberact.org/
AppliedML Days	26-30/03/2022	Lausanne, CH	https://appliedmldays.org/events/amld-epfl-2022
IEEE International Conference on Communications	16-20/05/2022	Seoul, SK	https://icc2022.ieee-icc.org/
RSA Conference	6-9/6/2022	San Francisco, US	https://www.rsaconference.com/usa
ACM FAccT Conference 2022	21-24/06/2022	Seoul, SK	https://facctconference.org/2022/
European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)	7-10/06/2022	Grenoble, FR	https://www.eucnc.eu/
IoT Week	20-23/06/2022	Dublin, IE	https://iotweek.org/
ACM MobiSys	25/06-01/07/2022	Portland, US	https://www.sigmobile.org/mobisys/2022/
IEEE ICDCS	10-13/07/2022	Bologna, IT	https://www.icdcs.org/
ACM MobiCom	oct-22	Sidney, AU	https://www.sigmobile.org/mobicom/2022/
ACM IMC	25-27/10/2022	Nice, FR	https://conferences.sigcomm.org/imc/2022/
ACM IoT Conference	7-10/11/2022	Delf, NL	https://iot-conference.org/iot2022/
ACM CoNext	6-9/12/2022	Rome, IT	https://conferences.sigcomm.org/co-next/2022/#!/home

TABLE 4. CONFERENCES AND JOURNALS FOR THE COMING YEAR.

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2.2 COMMUNICATION PLAN

Communication in Research and Innovation projects, is «a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures to communicate to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange»⁸. In the case of the **SPATIAL** project, Communication activities involve specific measures for promoting the project itself and the results attained. The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience, beyond the project's core community.

FIGURE 3. HOW TO COMMUNICATE YOUR PROJECT.

The plan herein has the mission to reach out to the broadest audience possible. Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the project lifetime to efficiently build traction among the target audience, emphasizing on SPATIAL's technological innovations and pilots' activities. Such campaigns will build upon the Promotion Mix -the fourth element of the

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Marketing Mix that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to initiate the engagement. In the case of SPATIAL this Promotion Mix is the integration of Personal Selling, Digital Marketing, Promotional Material and Branding

2.2.1 OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the communication strategy are as follows:

Set up internal communication mechanisms among the partners of the consortium;

- Support the external promotion of SPATIAL and its outcomes, managing the branding.
- Deliver top level messages about the project to all identified and relevant stakeholders.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of SPATIAL and its application in pilot activities.
- Increase awareness and interest about the project.

The following messages will be targeted to the different stakeholders group:

Stakeholder group	Main directions of the messages
AI Developers/ Engineers	Check the advances in the field of AI with the new algorithms
Cybersecurity providers	How cybersecurity is improved with the use of AI and our uses cases as samples.
End Users sector	Look what use cases we bring that you can also benefit from if you apply our advances.
Policy makers	AI explainability concept. No black boxes in AI anymore
Society as a whole	Usage of public funding to bring prosperous success for society in the field of AI.

TABLE 5. MAIN DIRECTION OF THE MESSAGES.

2.2.2 MEASURES

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A series of measures and communication tools will be implemented in order to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a communication friendly and to synchronous way.

PERSONAL SELLING		
Email Campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End User Sectors
<p>Broadcasting messages to a target pool of contact points via email is a highly effective measure of engagement, especially when promoting activities and outcomes, and seeking advocates in different communities. Email campaigns will be of interest when reaching out to networks of AI developers, cybersecurity providers and end users to promote new releases of code and announcements related to events, such as the educational module. SPATIAL will design and execute optimised templates for reaching out different target groups, defining specific call-to-actions to amplify the interaction and and visibility. The project will consider European GDPR-compliant solutions such as Sendinblue.</p>		
One-to-one Meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End User Sectors
<p>Although it is not a scalable mechanism, one-to-one phone calls and meetings are successful when targeting very specific key individuals, often as a follow-up of an email campaign or an event. For the scope of the project, this is especially relevant when engaging coordinators of AI communities, representatives of end use sectors, members of ECSO, and partners from related H2020 projects, especially as part of the periodic meetings and activities hosted by the different Working Groups.</p>		
DIGITAL CHANNELS		
Project Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	
<p>The main resource for generic promotion of the project activities and results to all target audiences, providing comprehensive information about SPATIAL, its objectives, and references to other resources. The first version is ready since month 2 and is maintained and updated regularly. Some relevant attributes will consider mobile-friendly design, quick loading times, accessibility, web analytics traffic tracking, search engine optimization and integration with relevant social media platforms. Link is https://spatial-h2020.eu</p>		
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	

SPATIAL will build and maintain actively its online presence in social media channels, with a focus on Twitter and LinkedIn. These channels have proven to be the most effective platforms when interacting with research and innovation communities, spreading out new publications and participation in different events. The project will leverage traffic from key partner accounts such as F-Secure ([75K+ followers](#)), Telefonica ([74K followers](#)), NEC ([14K](#)

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<p>followers) and Reaktor (15K+ followers), and timely contributions to the ECSO account (3K+ followers).</p>		
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Use Sectors
<p>Complementary to email engagement, online newsletters will spread out a snapshot of the main activities and opportunities in each period. Newsletters will anticipate planned actions for the upcoming periods, with special emphasis on workshops and events. The project will consider issuing its own newsletters and contributing to others with an already established member base.</p>		
Press Releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Use Sectors
<p>SPATIAL will take advantage of timely press releases published individually by some partners as an internal communication channel among their network of customers and members.</p>		
General Spreading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	
<p>Leveraging online publishing platforms will enable the project to reach out to a broader audience including professionals related to privacy and privacy management but also a non-specialised audience. Target platforms are the Research*EU Magazine, The Parliament Magazine, SciTech Europa and Open Access Government. Plus, SPATIAL will work to become CORDIS 'Project of the Month' to stand out among the most relevant projects of the H2020 framework. All partners will disclose non-confidential information of the project in their national language to local/regional newspapers and media.</p>		
Online Educational Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Use Sectors
<p>SPATIAL will leverage the platforms used by the consortium to publish the content of the educational module. This will include 'Elements of AI', co-hosted by Reaktor, as the platform to host the MOOC -with 500K students registered from 170 countries-, but will be complemented by alternatives such as the Fraunhofer Academy.</p>		
Developer Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers 	

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<p>SPATIAL will connect and execute periodic broad promotion activities in open communities and channels of developers, for instance Gitter communities, Women Who Code and Hashnode.</p>		
PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL		
Printed Material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	
<p>This represents the reference promotional instrument when participating in events. The most common items include brochures, catalogues, posters and any other laid out paper-based resource. Most of the PR material will be available as e-documents and printing will occur as required (e.g. for events, workshops, etc.). SPATIAL will explore other innovative alternatives to the traditional informative material. Labelled gadgets & merchandise (e.g. T-shirts, stickers) have turned out quite effective means of promotion among a less specialised audience, while encouraging a more sustainable approach when considering long-lasting items.</p>		
Slide Deck & Infographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Developers • Cybersecurity Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Use Sectors
<p>Digital slide decks and infographics are great instruments to quickly draw attention and share the vision and objectives of the project, often integrated with email campaigns, replacing in some cases the website as 'Point of Market Entry'. SPATIAL will produce several versions throughout its lifetime to fine-tune the content and shift progressively the focus to outcomes.</p>		
Multimedia Material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	
<p>The project will produce multimedia material to have a self-explanatory and appealing presentation of the project, leveraging other available distribution channels of promotion (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo). The team will organize a set of video interviews throughout the project.</p>		
BRANDING		
Logo & Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALL stakeholders 	
<p>SPATIAL will keep a brand that will be used, refined and protected throughout the project. A recognizable visual identity is provided at the proposal stage, to be adapted if required.</p>		

TABLE 6. MEASURES IMPLEMENTED WITHIN THE COMMUNICATION PLAN.

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2.3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

MONITORING

2.3.1 MONITORING STRATEGY

Monitoring and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication plan, in a frequent basis, is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

FIGURE 4. THE DISSEMINATION AND INNOVATION LOOP.

- **Design:** Design is activity based on the Dissemination & Communication Plan and the desired impact.
- **Execute:** Execute according to plan.
- **Monitor:** Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results. Monitoring will be based on a template that is available only to partners through the internal website.
- **Evaluate:** Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase.
- **Learn:** Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it.

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- **Adjust:** Absorb findings and lessons learnt adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given on the pre-assessment of information needs, on the monitoring frequency and the method of collecting evidence.

The execution and effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is depended to a close monitoring, flexible and prompt response mechanism. Every designed and implement activity will be monitored and evaluated according to its account and closely related to the KPIs.

2.3.2 POSSIBLE RISKS

There are a number of risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project. These risks will be monitored and mitigated by the Communication & Dissemination leader who will also control these risks on a regular basis and will report any changes to the Project Coordinator. Examples of communication risks include but are not limited to.

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RISK		
RISK	PRIORITY	MEASURE TO MINIMISE RISK
Covid19 Impact to dissemination and communication activities (especially physical events)	High	The Covid 19 pandemic is a reality that cannot be overlook, clearly posing a challenge towards dissemination & communication. For this reason, we foresee to implement additional online measures that do not reduce our presence as a project.
Communication and dissemination activities fail to target the correct audiences. The project may	High	SPATIAL partners have defined a clear set of objectives for each target group. However, this agile strategy allows us to revisit and mitigate our activities if needed. Close monitoring and frequent evaluations

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DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RISK		
fail to draw interest from relevant stakeholders		will make sure that our strategy will remain on track throughout the project.
Lack of public awareness of project activities	Low	The network is diverse and includes leading scientists, industrial partners, end users, standardization partners, etc. most of them affiliated to international Committees that Lack of public awareness of Low guarantee relevant connections and channels. If needed, Project activities extra budget coming from indirect costs or own resources will be directly allocated to perform any needed foreseen or unforeseen mitigation measures to meet project goals.

FIGURE 5. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RISKS.

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3 EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

3.1 EXPLOITATION PRINCIPLES

Public investment in Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program is established with a mission to generate new knowledge, new products, and services, but also non-technological and social innovation in order to foster the European Union economy, its development, competitiveness, and increase benefits to the EU citizens in general.

Consequently, one of the most important Horizon 2020's Rules for Participation is the beneficiaries' obligations to exploit and disseminate the outcomes of the funded activities.

Although interdependent and connected, dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium, a process of promotion and raising awareness to various stakeholder groups.

Communication differs as it incorporates strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Finally, Exploitation is the use of results in developing and commercialization of the product, process, or service, also creating further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, and standardization activities. All of this with the possibility of additional exploitation conditions in the European strategic interest.

For greater consistency, IPR protection and IPR strategy activities will be managed by Miguel García from AUS (leader of WP6) as Innovation and Exploitation Manager (IEM) with the support of the H2020 IPR Helpdesk⁹. He is appointed by the SC, as mentioned in D7.4 Quality

⁹ The IPR Helpdesk can be found at: <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk>

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Assurance plan. WP6 is responsible for the IPR plan (see Dissemination and Communication Plans (T6.2), and the Innovation Management, Exploitation and Sustainability (T6.3)).

This document summarizes the initial Exploitation plan with an overall exploitation strategy but is not fixed and it will evolve during the SPATIAL project and be detailed, and updated in both the Periodic and Final reports.

The basic principles for the Exploitation activities are as follows:

- a) Exploitation (dissemination and communication) plan should demonstrate a connection between the proposed activities and the expected impact of the SPATIAL project.
- b) Exploitation plan must have clear objectives adapted to the relevant target users
- c) Exploitation plan must include a strategy for the exploitation of results.

3.1.1 TECHNOLOGIES AND EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

Key Exploitable Results	Exploitation intentions
AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency and explainability; and certification	The results will be released in the form of specifications, technical documents, and code that will be made public available through open access (see Sec 2.2.1), so it can feed further research activities. These will facilitate the technological transfer of knowledge and techniques, and support the certification process.
Guidelines for AI applications, standardization paths, and initiate a and regulatory framework for Europe	The results will be made available via reports, technical documents, and standardization efforts. They will form the baseline for an improved regulatory framework.

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<p>Framework for verification and validation of software/hardware mechanisms, tools and system solutions that will provide the critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.</p>	<p>The framework will integrate the tools and solutions developed by SPATIAL. A joint exploitation strategy will be defined to offer services online, proposing a freemium model where certain assets will be made free-of-charge, while some features will be restricted through a service-fee mode.</p>
<p>A Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) for decentralized AI applications</p>	<p>TEE will be offered by the industrial partners NEC and FSC to provide AI-based applications with robustness to platform compromise. As such, users of AI systems will be able to trust the AI engine with the handling of their - potentially sensitive - data.</p> <p>NEC will enhance its data sharing/mining platform with TEE to resist powerful attacks and provide added value to its customers.</p>
<p>An educational module to provide technical skills, ethical and socio-legal awareness to ensure accountable development of security solutions.</p>	<p>The education module will be built and running in Reaktor Education platform, inside an ecosystem that provides sustainability for the long run. The platform offers a stable and tested environment, and the technical functionalities to grade exercises and generate certificates for successful completion. It is European made and hosted - follows naturally GDPR-regulation. Primary purpose is to educate future AI and machine learning engineers while they participate in traditional education programmes in universities. For support that purpose, all EU universities will be given</p>

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	<p>the possibility to add the course to their curriculum and credit their students without a fee by contacting the SPATIAL consortium and asking permission to do that. For universities outside Europe the use of the module in their curriculum will be negotiated case by case</p>
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TABLE 7. KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS.

3.1.2 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

SPATIAL will take the necessary steps of protecting the IP generated as part of the effort. All details regarding management and protection of knowledge created within SPATIAL are specified in the Consortium Agreement (CA) 8 Section: Results and 9 Access Rights, following well-known models, such as the DESCA 2020 Model Consortium Agreement.

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 26.2 with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed by the joint owners:

Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to Exploit the joint Results as it sees fit, and to grant non-exclusive licenses, without obtaining any consent from, paying compensation to, or otherwise accounting to any other joint owner.

However, for patent-protectable jointly-owned results, the following shall apply: The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related costs in advance of the Exploitation of the jointly-owned results. Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their patent-protectable jointly-owned results for research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).

Transfer of Results

Each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results following the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 30.

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It may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its Results to in Attachment (3) to this Consortium Agreement. The other Parties hereby waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement Article 30.1.

The transferring Party shall, however, at the time of the transfer, inform the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties will not be affected by such transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after the signature of this Agreement requires a decision of the Management Committee.

The Parties agree herein that each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results (including without limitations its share in Results that it owns jointly with another Party or Parties and all rights and obligations attached to such Results) to any of its Affiliated Entities without notification to any other Party. Each Party hereby waives any right to prior notification and to object to any transfers to a Party's Affiliated Entities. The transferring Party shall, however, upon another Party's request for Access Rights, inform the requesting Party of such transfer.

The Parties recognize that in the framework of a merger or an acquisition of an important part of its assets, it may be impossible under applicable EU and national laws on mergers and acquisitions for a Party to give the full 45 calendar days prior notice for the transfer as foreseen in the Grant Agreement.

Access Rights for Exploitation

The obligations above apply only for as long as other Parties still have - or still may request - Access Rights to the Results.

Access Rights to Results if Needed for Exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions.

Access rights to Results for internal research activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

Access Rights to Background if Needed for Exploitation of a Party's own Results, including for research on behalf of a third party, shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions.

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A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or, in the case of Section 9.7.2.1.2, after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

3.1.3 TARGET GROUPS

While target groups are already defined in the previous section of this document (page 11), the necessity for additional Target groups segmentation arrives from the different objectives, strategies and tactics that have to be employed for Exploitation of results, compared to those needed for Dissemination and Communication.

The basic starting criteria is whether SPATIAL Exploitation Results can be commercialized to a certain target group directly and immediately or not. If not, then they have to be subjected to Dissemination and Communication measures.

Segmentation will include an additional level of details depending on the nature of the target group as well including ones for identifying buyer personas within the buying center of Target groups.

A buying center, or decision-making unit, are all those members of an organization who become involved in the buying process for a particular product or service".

A buyer persona is a detailed description of someone from a target group organization and contains demographic details, interests, and behavioral traits, goals, pain points, and buying patterns.

Target Groups

i) AI Cybersecurity providers

These are companies that are using AI in their cybersecurity solutions, and as such the primary target group segment.

Further segmentation of this group conducts according to nine main areas in which they operate: Anti Fraud & Identity Management, Mobile Security, Predictive Intelligence, Behavioral Analytics / Anomaly Detection, Automated Security, Cyber-Risk Management, App Security, IoT Security, Deception Security.

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ii) System Integrators

System integrators are almost equally very important target segments, as AI Cybersecurity providers, considering that they have a large number of relevant partners and customers who belong to the end-user stakeholder domain of the SPATIAL project, and additionally great influence on them since end-user stakeholders don't have sufficient human and technological resources to cover cybersecurity matters.

Further segmentation of the System Integrator segment conducts according to size: big, medium, and small.

iii) Academia & RTOs

This target group is relevant for the SPATIAL result of the educational module which will provide technical skills, ethical and socio-legal awareness for accountable development of security solutions.

Further segmentation of this segment conducts according to the geographical area, with regards to the most rational strategy of exploitation that should be from local towards global markets: EU, North America, Asia Pacific, Latin America, Middle East and Africa

3.1.4 MARKET DOMAINS

The history of technology is riddled with unintended consequences. As cyber fiction writer William Gibson said, "...the street finds its own uses for things." The ubiquitous digitization in every domain opened wide doors for data and security breaches, resulting in cyber-crime. In the past decade, hackers have targeted major corporations around the world, electrical grids, uranium enrichment facilities, hospitals, universities, voting systems in the United States. It seems that there is no area and sector that is not attacked.

However, clear understanding of the market and subsequent domains are starting point for successful Exploitation of results. Market domains are presented in following table:

By Product Type	Identity and Access Management	
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	Threat Detection and Prevention (Unified Threat Management and Threat Mitigation) Security and Vulnerability Management DDoS Mitigation Next Generation Firewall IDS/IPS Security Information and Event Management Email Security Endpoint Security IoT Security Other Solutions	
By Deployment	On-cloud On-premise	
By End-user Industry	Aerospace, Defense, and Intelligence Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance Healthcare Manufacturing Retail Public Utility IT and Telecommunication Other End-user Industries	
By Geography	North America	United States Canada
	Europe	United Kingdom Germany France Rest of Europe
	Asia Pacific	China Japan India South Korea Rest of Asia Pacific
	Latin America	Brazil Argentina Mexico Rest of Latin America

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	Middle East and Africa	United Arab Emirates Saudi Arabia South Africa Rest of Middle East and Africa
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TABLE 8. MARKET DOMAINS.

3.2 EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

3.2.1 REQUIREMENTS FROM THE GRANT AGREEMENT

Under the section 28.1 Obligation to exploit the results are defined:

Each beneficiary must – up to four years after the period set out in Article 3 – take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing; see Article 30) by:

- a) using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- c) creating and providing a service, or
- d) using them in standardization activities.

This does not change the security obligations in Article 37, which still apply.

3.2.2 INDIVIDUAL PARTNERS’ INITIAL EXPLOITATION PLAN

During the proposal phase, interested partners had defined their exploitation plans.

However, during the SPATIAL project lifecycle, these plans will evolve and be further refined using exploitation tools and methodologies on dedicated workshops and activities.

PARTNER	INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS
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<p>TUD</p>	<p>As the SPATIAL coordinator, TU Delft intends to create a knowledge hub of trustworthy AI, which can serve as a channel to showcase the SPATIAL results and to engage companies and the non-academic sector/private sectors. As a research institute, TU Delft will convey the SPATIAL solutions and findings both to scientific output and demonstrate their achievements by organizing international workshops and symposiums such as ACM EdgeSys and FCN. By integrating and evaluating SPATIAL solutions through testbeds at TU Delft, the knowledge transfer activities will lead to an enhancement of research profile, awareness of trustworthy AI, and increased funding opportunities. TU Delft will convey research outcomes into educational modules with the ongoing activities of TUD AiTech, and also with NWO Gravitation Consortium on "Hybrid Intelligence" and "Ethics of Socially Disruptive Technologies"</p>
<p>FSC</p>	<p>FSC will share and promote the results to FSC's Business Units, in particular, "Managed Detection and Response unit and Cyber Security Consulting". SPATIAL results on attacks and resilience of AI-based systems used in cybersecurity will be practically valuable primarily for FSC's Rapid Detection and Response (RDR) and Protection Service for Business (PSB) product lines. This will also benefit the cybersecurity consultants, in particular, in security assessment-related customer projects (there is a growing interest of our customers in understanding weaknesses of ML applications in malware and dynamic attack detection). Technology transfer and integration will be the main exploitation approach.</p>
<p>MI</p>	<p>Montimage has built and commercializes a security monitoring and enforcement framework for 4G/5G/IoT networks (MMT) and a fully portable 4G/5G mobile network solution that will be one of the use cases testbeds for validating the results of the project. These products require advanced analytics based on AI/ML techniques applicable in different use cases. The results of SPATIAL will be of great importance to improve these techniques, particularly concerning the use, resiliency, explainability and assessment of AI/ML. SPATIAL will allow improving the use and explainability of AI/ML techniques for our different use cases (cybersecurity analysis and protection of 5G and IoT networks, analysis of encrypted traffic, Root Cause Analysis). It will also allow developing metrics for the assessment of AI/ML</p>

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	<p>techniques, optimizing them using distributed ML data and processing, extending the training, penetration testing and cyber range capabilities with new explainable and adversarial AI/ML techniques.</p>
<p>MFX</p>	<p>Mainflux provides a unified IoT platform with the cloud-edge continuum for the development of IoT solutions, applications and smart connected products, recognized by the Linux Foundation and industry leaders such as Dell and Intel. SPATIAL facilitates a second phase in this strategy, developing vertical solutions on top of the IoT platform: i) systematic investigation and proper variation of the needs for authentication, authorization, and accounting services across IoT devices/ecosystems with the definition of appropriate system architectures and implementation approaches; ii) A set of accountable AI algorithm(s) designed specifically for cybersecurity, methods to enable model distillation for pre-trained ML models, certification methods for AI-based products and their security-related operations; iii) Design mechanisms for trusted executions of AI applications, security standards for AI-based decentralized deployments, set of solutions to aid the deployment of secure AI-based solutions such as rich-media emergency call systems.</p>
<p>TID</p>	<p>TID has plans to introduce the results of SPATIAL to Telefonica Operating Businesses, by running demonstrators and trials and seeking to find applications within their businesses. Telefonica is currently developing and extending its next (fourth) generation platform that will make cognitive sense of a flow of data, also at the edge nodes, and will facilitate the discovery of new value-added propositions based on the insights from the SPATIAL. Being part of a telecom operator, TID is especially interested in the novel edge/cloud data services and how they could be applicable in both fixed and mobile environments, transferring results to the ElevenPaths business unit focused on cybersecurity B2B services. The work done within the project can provide guidelines for edge/cloud network planning, orchestration and design, as well as to understand trade-offs between resource and QoE for SPATIAL.</p>

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<p>FOKUS</p>	<p>Fraunhofer FOKUS pursues the goal to increase the knowledge and technical level of the institute's portfolio within SPATIAL. Thereby, FOKUS intends to benefit and acquire critical know-how for the relevant methods, platforms, techniques and solutions which will be developed during the execution. As an applied research institute, FOKUS intends to make this know-how and scientific results available to industrial organizations and public entities in the form of workshops, as well as articles in journals and scientific magazines. Further exploitation activities of relevance will be conducted through training courses, presentations at workshops and conferences, and activities in standardization bodies, university lectures and demonstrations at industrial fairs/events. Through our close contacts to Berlin's academic network, we plan to exploit the results in the course of lectures, student projects and master and bachelor theses.</p>
<p>UCD</p>	<p>UCD will be contributing to scientific and technical publications in high impact journals and conferences. Being a higher education as well as a research-oriented institution, UCD intends to exploit the knowledge through dissertations. The know-how gained by the involvement in this project will be used to enrich our project portfolio and clientele, combined with other AI projects being carried out at the Insight Center, CCI (Centre for Cybersecurity and Cybercrime Investigation), CeADAR, and PEL (Performance Engineering Lab). This will help UCD to develop a comprehensive knowledge in AI and security domains which will lead to more directly engage the local industry. The material will also be used to develop new courses at both Bachelor level and postgraduate level. UCD is delivering modules that are focused on industry training, hence this project will open up a possibility to design AI related training programmes for technological partners that are already collaborating with the university.</p>
<p>UT</p>	<p>UT plans to extend the concept of explainable devices to autonomous unmanned vehicles, which is a 5- year ongoing project supported by the IT Estonian Academy and started in October 2019. We expect to have at least two PhD dissertations as an outcome from the project. We are interested in designing an educational framework that can be used with rapid prototyping platforms, such as Raspberry Pi and Arduino, and behavior of AI when designing IoT prototypes.</p>

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<p>NEC</p>	<p>NEC Laboratories Europe is in constant discussion with the Business Units and intends to use the results in future products. Expanding on its SaaS, IaaS and thin client solutions, NEC plans to use this technology to enhance current products in this area by focusing on production-ready security components, thereby making them more attractive and competitive in the market. The research laboratory is a member of the Hyperledger project and is in contact with the relevant units for the operations and development for blockchain and fintech divisions. In addition to its infrastructure and cloud services, NEC is a cloud application developer for its own end-users and as a system integrator.</p>
<p>EUR</p>	<p>EUR will focus on two primary issues that the SPATIAL project will further develop. First, EUR will exploit the knowledge and understanding it gains through embedded social science analysis to determine best practices and policy guidelines related to the effective implementation of new technologies. This is critical for understanding not only technical developments, but how new technologies are embedded in socio-political environments. Second, EUR will focus on exploiting effective learning strategies gained from the development of the education module. As experts in communication practice, EUR already has experience in engaging different stakeholders including policy makers, however specific technical communities require a different type of engagement and learning strategies.</p>
<p>AUS</p>	<p>AUSTRALO will leverage the outcomes of SPATIAL in its mission to bridge the divide between the high-tech Research and Innovation and the market, in this particular case with special emphasis in the uptake of trustworthy AI. This will be achieved by exploiting the knowledge acquired in previous and ongoing projects with a focus on marketing services and ecosystem dynamization. Participating in SPATIAL is an opportunity to contribute to the promotion and validation of AI technology in the European market, reinforcing and enlarging our portfolio of technical partners. This will allow the organization to expand our range of services towards other customers and partners.</p>
<p>REA</p>	<p>Reaktor's plan is to develop a modern and highly engaging educational module that serves the needs of the academic and industry partners by bridging the gap between</p>

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	<p>academic research and effective dissemination. The module will boost visibility of the RE educational platform via new and topical content, open discussions with stakeholders interested in the topic outside the consortium, and will also be used to train employees internally.</p>
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TABLE 9. EXPLOITATION PLAN PER PARTNER.

3.2.3 EXPLOITATION DELIVERABLES AND CONTENTS

Exploitation measures and activities are planned within the WP6

Impact, Outreach and Collaboration as Task 6.3 Innovation Management, Exploitation and Sustainability (M6 - M36). The task objective is O6.3: Assess the project footprint through performance indicators, while developing exploitation, sustainability and business models of the key results to be delivered. Related deliverables are:

D6.1 : SPATIAL Impact Master Plan [M06]

Master plan for the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies (T6.2, T6.3) designed for the project. The plan will also provide an overview of the stakeholder base to target (T6.1), as well as a standardization landscape as the basis for further standardization activities in the project (T6.4)

D6.3 : Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report [M36]

Report of indicators, measures and elements designed and released in SPATIAL Impact Master Plan through the first period of the project (T6.3 and T6.4).

D6.5 : Impact Assessment and Exploitation Final Report [M36]

Report of indicators, measures and elements designed and released in SPATIAL Impact Master Plan through the first period of the project (T6.3 and T6.4).

3.2.4 TOOLS AND METHODOLOGIES TO SUPPORT EXPLOITATION

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The exploitation of results mostly belongs to the business and commercialization domain which, similarly to science, tends to base its activity on comprehensive analysis, examination of the hypothesis, reaching certainty and achieving planned and expected results.

As in science for that purpose, numerous kinds of methodologies, frameworks, tools and models are used, with the basic understanding that there is no perfect model and therefore in order to attain certainty using a multitude of them is the basic principle.

The purpose of the planned Tools and Methodologies for Exploitation of SPATIAL results is exactly to secure maximization of the commercialization, use and sustainability of SPATIAL results by the scientific, economic, or public stakeholders, transforming R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.

In the following paragraph, numerous methodologies and tools are introduced. For further questions regarding these methodologies and tools, Australo can provide information on the source.

Selected tools will be used within the SPATIAL methodology' multi-stage process:

- **Key Exploitable Results** for the identification of Spatial' different types of exploitable results of the project as a whole.
- **The exploitation matrix** designed with a goal to support partners to define the results that each partner plans to exploit, initial value proposition conceived that these results have and their strategy.

Organization	Type of Organization			
KER Key Exploitable Results	YOUR ROLE IN EXPLOITATION <i>Please note that you are one of the owners of the exploitable result if you contributed to its development. You are a beneficiary partner if you are</i>	TARGET SECTOR <i>Please describe your target sector of application, try to be as specific as possible in the description.</i>	TARGET AUDIENCE <i>Please describe the target users/clients/audience of your exploitation activity, trying to be as specific as possible.</i>	VALUE PROPOSITION <i>Please describe the value proposition results that you planning to exploit have for your target audience</i>

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	interested in exploiting a result produced by other partners			

TABLE 10. KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS TABLE.

- **Market Readiness Assessment.** A planning tool that will include periodic (re-)assessments combined with goal-setting future scores of the project based on several indicators, Project Market Background, Project Market Background, Indicative Social Return on Investment (SROI), Barriers and risks for exploitation, Opportunities and growth strategy
- **Business model canvas** briefly outline a set of hypotheses that have to be tested and refined throughout the project lifetime and provides inputs for the development of a business plan

PROBLEM <small>List your top 1-3 problems.</small>	SOLUTION <small>Outline a possible solution for each problem.</small>	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION <small>Single, clear, compelling message that states why you are different and worth paying attention.</small>	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE <small>Something that cannot easily be bought or copied.</small>	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS <small>List your target customers and users.</small>
	KEY METRICS <small>List the key numbers that tell you how your business is doing.</small>		CHANNELS <small>List your path to customers (inbound or outbound).</small>	
EXISTING ALTERNATIVES <small>List how these problems are solved today.</small>		HIGH-LEVEL CONCEPT <small>List your fit for Y analogy e.g. YouTube = Flickr for video.</small>		EARLY ADOPTERS <small>List the characteristics of your ideal customers.</small>
COST STRUCTURE <small>List your fixed and variable costs.</small>		REVENUE STREAMS <small>List your sources of revenue.</small>		

FIGURE 6. BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS TEMPLATE.

- **Value Proposition Canvas** framework enables to 1) precisely understand the target profiles' needs; 2) visualize the value created, creating gains; and 3) achieve product-market fit

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strategy, the financial background, and containing a projected profit and loss statement.

ER1 (Exploitable Result 1)	
Main Exploiter	
Main innovation content	
Cost Structure	€ xxx (Average Account size); Annual Support subscription package - xxxx €; Professional services – xxxx €
Revenue Streams	
Main identified customer(s)	
Market and its size	
Positioning	Value proposition
	Competitors

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	Value for outbidding competition	
	Protection vs competitors	
Time to market		
Issues to be solved during the project		

TABLE 11. KER ASSESSMENT TABLE

Product or Service	Predicted price	2024		2026		2028	
		QTY	Rev. [k€]	QTY	Rev. [k€]	QTY	Rev. [k€]
	xxx € / unit	x	xx	x	xxx	x	xxx
	xxx € / unit	x	xx	x	xxx	xxx	xxx
SUM		xxx		xxx		xxx	

TABLE 12. FIGURES PROJECTIONS.

- **Buying persona Canvas.** A buyer persona is a detailed description of someone who represents your target audience. It contains demographic details, interests, and

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behavioral traits, goals, pain points, and buying patterns. It enables them to craft marketing messages targeted specifically to them.

<p>Buyer Persona</p> <p>Who are our buyers? What is the archetype of our buyers? What is their archetypal background? What is their archetypal experience? What is their archetypal balance of professional and personal lives? What are their areas of focus and responsibilities? What are the archetypal roles in organizations?</p>	<p>Goals</p> <p>What are our buyer's business goals? What are our buyer's personal goals? What organizational goals affect their buying behavior?</p>	<p>Buying Process</p> <p>What buying process do our buyers follow? What is their archetypal buyer's journey? How does procurement govern the buying process?</p>	<p>Buyer Thinking</p> <p>Which attitudes hurt/help us on the part of buyers? What perceptions & beliefs do our buyers have? How does buyer thinking affect buying behavior?</p>	<p>Why Buy</p> <p>How do our buyers make choices? What risks affect buying choices? How do our buyers balance consequences and payoffs? How does buyer thinking affect "why" choices? What are the unlocked drivers for decisions? What are the unarticulated "why" reasons for decisions?</p>
	<p>Initiatives</p> <p>What are the archetypal initiatives of our buyers? What are the archetypal strategies of our buyers and industry? Which programs & projects are important?</p>	<p>Timing</p> <p>What are the seasonal patterns of our buyers? How does formal budget planning affect timing? What is normal end-to-end buying cycle?</p>	<p>Channels</p> <p>Which channels do our buyers use? Where are our buyers socially? What external sources do they frequent?</p>	
<p>Influencers, Stakeholders, Buying Team</p> <p>Who are key stakeholders? Who are internal influencers? External influencers? Who participates on buying team? What role does buyer persona have on buying team? Who participates in the approval process?</p>		<p>Content and Information</p> <p>What information and data references do buyers rely on? How do buyers utilize and share content? What types of content affects purchase decisions? What are content buyers seek and when? How buyers obtain and receive information?</p>		

FIGURE 9. BUYER PERSONA CANVAS.

● Go-to Market plan

FIGURE 10. GO TO MARKET PLAN.

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The go-to-Market plan is taken from Andreessen Horowitz's private venture capital firm Startup Bootcamp.

Before founding a venture capital firm, Marc Andreessen and Ben Horowitz created Netscape and Javascript language, Firefox and Mozilla Foundation, as well as two companies that started from zero and acquired for more than one billion dollars to HP.

The portfolio of their venture capital firm includes Skype, Twitter, Facebook, and GitHub.

The go-to-market plan was created by four other partners of Andreessen Horowitz. Previously their VP of sales they were responsible for the above-mentioned companies' successful acquisitions and created the plan for the startup companies they invested in.

It details the critical path to marketing for growth. From identifying a value proposition and a customer segment and selling to them, it covers the full spectrum of internal and external positioning, aligning the value props, planning campaigns and analyzing results.

Exploitation Methodology Process

SPATIAL methodology' multi-stage process is structured in the following phases:

- i) Creation of Market Readiness Assessment.
- ii) Identification of individual KERs, their initial value proposition, and partners Exploitation strategy with the exploitation matrix tool.
- iii) Workshop for developing Business Value Proposition Canvas
- iv) Workshop for assembling Business model canvas
- v) Creation of a Business plan
- vi) Creation of Buying persona Canvas and relevant messaging
- vii) Refining and utilizing Go-to-Market plan

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4 STANDARDIZATION

One of the key challenges relating to AI and cybersecurity is provided by the need to establish corresponding processes and regulations, in order to introduce AI in critical infrastructures in an accountable and trustful manner. To support these processes, the SPATIAL project plans to make steps towards influencing the governance structure in this regard and basically work towards effective regulation, governance and standardization processes and procedures for AI use in ICT systems and cybersecurity. This includes the need to define metrics for understanding *what attackers can achieve* and with *what resources and capabilities*. Based on such metrics and agreed standards developers and service providers will be in a better position to make optimal choices when having to optimally configure their systems. Utilizing such metrics, it should be possible to obtain relevant evidence for the AI based systems in question, in terms of their resilience properties and to communicate those to customers, certification bodies and regulators.

The corresponding T6.4 in SPATIAL is responsible for identifying and enforcing synergies with standardization bodies and activities at different levels, e.g., European or international level. Leveraging the active position of some partners in SDOs (Standards Development Organisation), technical committees and task forces, SPATIAL plans to establish collaborations with a bidirectional purpose: (i) integrate latest results in transparency, explainability and end use validation of AI to the activities of the project; (ii) propose relevant contributions to the activities of relevant SDOs, either in the form of results achieved (e.g. DIN SPECs on AI quality models) or activities to co-develop new insights (e.g. SPEC-groups within the German AI-standardization roadmap of DIN). SPATIAL will also create a line of collaboration with StandICT.eu - the European ICT Standardization Observatory and Support Facility.

4.1 FUNDAMENTALS

Within the following sections, we shortly describe the type of standards we would like to address. Thereby, the provided definitions are not strictly worked out according to the available

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standard forms within the various SDOs, but rather represent the SPATIAL view on standardization. Hence, this means that the project plans to work towards documents of the following types and if reasonable submit those in the specific form of the selected SDO. Please note that various SDOs provide the option to utilize different standards and semi-standards - with varying scopes and definitions - and an analysis of all these types will go beyond the current scope.

Besides the different types of standards, the following paragraphs briefly describe the various levels of standardization, such as national, European, world-wide as well as belonging SDOs of potential relevance for SPATIAL. This is complemented by the involvement of the project partners in different working groups and SDOs presented later on in the document.

4.1.1 TYPE OF STANDARDS

Various types of standards are relevant for the activities of the SPATIAL project. These include specifications, technical reports, normative documents, *request for comments* and general standards, which are worked out as a final result of a particular standardization activity. Please note that each standardization body has its own terminology in this regard. For the purposes of SPATIAL, we only mention the most relevant type of standards, which should not mean however that the SPATIAL consortium is not going to pursue other options if deemed reasonable during the project execution.

Specifications: Specifications are often worked out and provided by some SDOs and umbrella organizations. In general, they are meant to outline a particular architecture and play an important role especially in the ICT domain. Specifications are often not considered to be “real standards” but fast track documents, which address the current ICT needs in a domain in question and are normally updated on a regular basis. Specifications can be used as a document showing consensus between a group of industrial and academic partners as well as end-users on a particular topic, and can be the base for defining products and serve as intermediate steps towards long-term standards.

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Technical reports: Technical reports (TRs) are documents that describe concrete architecture and example/reference implementations, thereby demonstrating feasibility or pointing to potential pitfalls/issues when implementing a standard or specification.

Normative documents: By normative documents we denote norms, which are established standards and have passed the different levels of standardization. Thereby, it should be noted that norms take a longer time and process to be established

Request for comments: Requests for comments (RFCs) are the typical standards of IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) and constitute a set of documents that define the architectures and mechanisms in various wide-spread communication networks and protocols. RFCs are initiated by a draft that is submitted to and discussed within a particular working group. Given that a draft is approved, it turns into an RFC which on the other hand can be declared obsolete after a while and substituted by a newer updated version.

General standards: By general standards, we denote documents issued by an SDO which have been an established and well-known standard for a while and have been implemented in different products. These general standards might include directives, architectures and normative documents, which are of wide relevance for the domain in question.

4.1.2 LEVELS OF STANDARDISATION WORK

Different levels of standardization can be considered within SPATIAL. Indeed, the project will consider contributing on national, European and world-wide level standards if applicable.

National: Standardization often starts at national level, e.g., in SDOs such as the DIN Germany. The corresponding specifications, norms or standards can be further contributed up the standardization chain on European or directly on international level.

European: On European level, we can observe mainly the CEN/CENELEC standardization body, which is the umbrella organization for all local European national SDOs (e.g. for the DIN).

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However, there are also additional/parallel standardization paths - for example the industrial driven standardization at ETSI, which might be of relevance for SPATIAL.

World-wide: On an international level, there are the ISO standards which encapsulate the national SDOs world-wide (including examples such as DIN and CEN/CENELEC). Furthermore, SDOs such as ITU-T take care of specific domains such as telecommunication, whilst other local/national standards (e.g. from IETF, ETSI, DIN, OMG, ...) can play a vital role on the world-wide domain with their acceptance across the world.

4.2 LANDSCAPE

The following two subsections provide an overview of relevant committees and standards, which should be monitored by the SPATIAL project and for which corresponding contributions can be made, or liaisons can be established. In this context, the following committees and standards are mainly relating to the aspects of explainability, accountability, ethical and trustworthiness aspects of AI/ML.

4.2.1 COMMITTEES

Following relevant committees/initiatives were identified:

- **DIN** German National AI Roadmap
- **ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42** Artificial intelligence
- **CEN/CENELEC** Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence

4.2.2 STANDARDS

The following list provides an overview of some of the key standards and ongoing standardization activities. These will be considered by the SPATIAL project when looking at how to transfer the obtained research results towards standardization and industrial exploitation. Thereby, as mentioned before, the selected standards relate to the topics of explainability and quality assurance of AI/ML based systems:

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- **DIN SPEC 92001-1:2019-04:** Artificial Intelligence - Life Cycle Processes and Quality Requirements - Part 1: Quality Meta Model
- **DIN SPEC 92001-2:** Artificial Intelligence – Life Cycle Processes and Quality Requirements – Part 2: Robustness
- **ISO/IEC TR 24368:** Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Overview of ethical and societal concerns
- **ISO/IEC TR 29119-11 :2020:** Software and systems engineering – Software testing – Part 11: Guidelines on the testing of AI-based systems
- **ISO/IEC CD 23894:** Information Technology – Artificial Intelligence – Risk Management
- **ISO/IEC DTS 4213:** Information technology – Artificial Intelligence – Assessment of machine learning classification performance
- **ISO/IEC AWI TR 5469:** Artificial intelligence – Functional safety and AI systems
- **ISO/IEC DTR 24027:** Information Technology – Artificial Intelligence – Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making
- **ISO/IEC 24668:** Information Technology – Artificial Intelligence – Process management framework for Big data analytics
- **ISO/IEC 24028:** Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence
- **ISO/IEC TR 24029-1:** Artificial Intelligence (AI) – Assessment of the robustness of neural networks – Part 1: Overview
- **ISO/IEC 23053:** Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)
- **ISO/IEC 38507:** Information technology – Governance of IT – Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations

4.3 STANDARDIZATION PLAN

The T6.4 activities of SPATIAL will continuously screen and identify significant opportunities to push contributions into future standards, pre-normative activities and collaborative

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development environments that are meaningful for the scope of the project. Senior members of the consortium will be appointed to participate in relevant working groups and technical committees, to ensure an active representation. In this context, the appointed representatives will be reporting - within the project consortium - about latest advances and raising awareness regarding potential collaboration efforts. In addition, timely contributions will be driven and carried out by individual partners on behalf of the project through their delegates.

4.3.1 LIASON WITH COMMITTEES

The following liaisons and participation in particular committees are envisioned as of now in the course of SPATIAL:

3GPP: SPATIAL will be formally represented by TID delegates participating on behalf of its institution, raising awareness of opportunities and pursuing contributions.

ETSI: TID Telefonica is part of the Technical Steering committees of NFV and PDL groups, and also participates as contributors in the groups ENI, SAI and ZSM. TID will disseminate to these groups the outcomes from SPATIAL and will also communicate responses and recommendations back to the consortium.

ETSI DTS/CYBER-0050: Cybersecurity in relation to IoT products – i.e., all the activities relating to AI and IoT have the potential to constitute valuable contributions in this scope. Furthermore, Explainability and Cybersecurity aspects constitute potential inputs to this group.

IRTF: TID is either co-chairing or participating as a contributor to the following groups - COINRG, DINRG, NMRG and QIRG - and will increase awareness in the corresponding groups regarding the research and experimentation activities performed in SPATIAL.

IETF: TID is contributing in the working groups on trusted environments (WGs TEEP and PANIC) and security management (WG I2NSF). These groups are directly interested in cybersecurity technologies - correspondingly SPATIAL's outcomes on trusted and decentralized AI will be presented in this scope. Within the COINRG group, TUD has the potential to contribute on the topic of trustworthy Edge AI - e.g. on the problem statement definition - and the belonging requirement analysis.

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StandICT.eu: SPATIAL plans to leverage on the involvement of AUSTRALO as a member of the H2020 StandICT.eu project, which constitutes the European ICT Standardization Observatory and Support Facility.

4.3.2 CONTRIBUTION TO STANDARDS UNDER DEVELOPMENT

The project and correspondingly its senior members plan to contribute and play a vital role in the following standards and belonging collaboration activities.

DIN Smart City Forum: FOKUS plans to contribute methods for AI explainability in the scope of DIN SPECs for Smart Cities. The further updates to this DIN SPEC will include results from the SPATIAL projects in terms of the applicability of AI in the domain of Smart Cities and Communities. Furthermore, the topic of certification of Smart City solutions is gaining momentum, hence the aspects of explainability and accountability will be very important towards establishing a certification scheme for AI based solutions in this context.

DIN Artificial Intelligence Standardization Roadmap: In addition, FOKUS is involved in the definition of the German *DIN Artificial Intelligence Standardization Roadmap*. In this context, FOKUS plays a role in different topics, such as aspects of AI for security as well as the potential for the certification of AI based on metrics for explainability and accountability.

5G PPP Pre-Standardization WG: TID is a member of the 5G PPP and participates in meetings and other dissemination events on a regular basis. As a 5G PPP contributor, TID has the potential to transfer the SPATIAL results to this Public Private Partnership and to push for recommendations for the implementation of AI in the scope of 5G and Edge Computing.

4.3.3 NEW STANDARDS

Cooperation with the cybersecurity sector - including SDOs, umbrella organizations and regulators - will ensure the application of transparency and explainability of AI in the development of security solutions. In order to support this process, SPATIAL plans the publication of research insights, the description of technical implementations, explicit contribution to standards and the definition of new standards.

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The active participation of FSC, TID and UT as members of the European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO) will facilitate fruitful collaborations and synergies with the activities of the Cyber Security Public-Private Partnership, as well as the dissemination of relevant standardizable SPATIAL results among over 250 members of the European security industry and research community. Leveraging on this potential, the SPATIAL consortium members plan to identify gaps and define new standards where appropriate.

The technical ambition of SPATIAL to go beyond the state-of-art will encourage an active contribution to SDOs, technical committees and working groups - such contributions bear the potential to result in new standards in case none of the existing ones can accommodate the relevant SPATIAL results. These activities are aligned with the strategic goal of the European Commission for setting up clear ICT standardization requirements for the Digital Single Market. Furthermore, SPATIAL will produce guidelines for AI based systems and will work out some potential inputs towards a belonging governance and regulatory framework for Europe. The corresponding results will be made available via reports, technical documents, and standardization efforts, such that they can provide a baseline for an improved regulatory framework.

4.3.4 DEVELOPMENT OF NEW SPECIFICATIONS

A major goal of SPATIAL is to support the availability of better certification and automated assessment frameworks for secure networks and systems, allowing better-informed investment decisions related to security and privacy. The belonging guidelines, architectures and structures have the potential to turn into a new specification (e.g., within DIN).

SPATIAL aims to provide a framework for the explainability of AI based security methods. Moreover, the project will work towards establishing various tests in control environments and in a trial setup. In addition, SPATIAL envisions working out some procedures for the testing and assessment of AI based cybersecurity, in order to enable improved understanding of the ML model quality and resilience. Such information can be used in the course of corresponding investments in security and privacy. This approach requires a set of metrics to quantify the

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explainability of an AI based system. Furthermore, a process should be defined regarding how to add explainability features to existing AI algorithms, ML pipelines and ML models.

As we can see, the above elucidations clearly provide material for at least one new specification. The exact contributions and scope will need to mature in the course of the project as the partners proceed with their development.

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5 CONCLUSION

On a clear vision to generate impact, the Spatial Impact Master Plan clearly defines the fundamentals for maximizing reach, commercial approach and scientific relevance. This deliverable emphasizes a good number of activities framed into one of the three axes for impact within the project: communication, dissemination and exploitation.

The joint effort provided by the consortium assures and adequate impact management all through the project lifetime, clearly underscoring the actions and activities linked to it. Additionally, the project presents a clear plan on how standardization will play a significant role in our activities, identifying the actors, committees and responsibilities attached to bring the results to the relevant spots to address improvements in current technological standards.

SPATIAL will bring forward a remarkable set of results in the areas of artificial intelligence, explainability and cybersecurity which will be key elements of impact of the project as such, but also the use of Horizon 2020 in research and innovation activities.

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6 APPENDIX A. MINDMAP

